

DIFFICULTIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO FRESHMEN IN NON- PHILOLOGICAL HIGHER EDUCATION

Abdukhafizova Nargiza

English teacher Department of Theoretical Aspects of English
Uzbek State World Languages University, Tashkent

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Abstract. The article being talked about thinks about issues of showing tuning in foreign language classes to students of non-philological higher instructive establishments. The writer of the article considers that examining this question stays real because at the cutting edge transformative phase of a calculated science listening is considered a key ability in showing a foreign language that targets dominating a foreign language in general. Perceptions of methodologists over the instructive process have shown that students who are not explicitly educated to discernment by hearing, listening abilities are not created. The abilities are not acquired naturally, they are framed through escalated listening practice in a foreign language class.

Keywords: listening, foreign language classes, students, learning process, auditory skills, development, relevant, perception, non-philological.

Introduction. The English abilities, the capacity to recognize and get what others are talking about, on account of educating in foreign language illustrations, is the comprehension of a foreign language discourse during its entry. This incorporates understanding the speaker's articulation, linguistic designs, and jargon. The issue of showing listening understanding is one of the main parts of showing foreign language correspondence, and for that reason, it is urgent to foster listening understanding advancements altogether to satisfy the needs of the time. We experience tuning in as an independent discourse action in different genuine correspondence circumstances. This happens when we pay attention to different declarations; radio and TV news; different guidelines and errands; addresses; the tales of individuals we converse with; exhibitions by entertainers; the questioner by telephone, and so on the targets of listening preparing can be characterized as follows: to foster specific abilities; to create certain discourse abilities; to figure out how to convey; to foster vital capacities and mental capacities; to retain discourse material; to train students to comprehend the importance of a solitary assertion; to help students to feature what is significant in the progression of data; to foster hear-able memory; create a hear-able reaction. When performing listening tasks, the speaker should exhibit the accompanying capacities: foresee what individuals will say; surmise new words and expressions without alarm; use his past information as a reason for comprehension; understand the speaker's demeanor to the subject of discussion; have the capacity to take notes as indicated by the hour of tuning in; comprehend the inflection what's

more accents; comprehend the moral side of talking, the principles of conversation, banter and different sorts of debates.^[1]

Troubles connected with language viewpoints and challenges connected with discourse qualities. Hardships connected with language perspectives can be partitioned into three gatherings:

1. Phonetic. Under this supposition, there is no reasonable limit between sounds in the word and between words in the progression of discourse. Two parts of listening are recognized: phonemic (impression of individual phonetic peculiarities at the degree of words and designs) and discourse, which incorporates the most common way of perceiving the entire setting. It ought to be noticed that when figuring out how to pay attention to real materials it is important to foster discourse hearing. The person's way of talking can be exceptionally different and present hardships for its discernment and understanding. In the native language, this trouble is made up for by broad tuning in practice, yet students have extremely restricted experience paying attention to foreign language discourse.

Normally, any singular elocution includes the tone of the voice, a genuinely high speed, and certain discourse deformities that will make it hard to comprehend. To beat the challenges related to understanding local speakers' discourse, it is important to pay attention to their discourse from the start of preparing, bit by bit lessening the quantity of showing texts needed by the instructor. It ought to likewise be recalled that the more local speakers (men, ladies, kids) a student tunes in to, the more straightforward it is to adjust to the singular way of talking. It is subsequently important to make broad utilization of learning and credible accounts, including the logical materials we have highlighted.

2. Grammatical. Various syntactic troubles are associated above all else with the presence of syntactic structures, not unconventional to the Uzbek language. Seeing an expression, the understudy ought to partition it into discrete components, for example, enlightening indications of the sounding expression, which are genuinely communicated by comparing discourse characteristics. There are three genuinely communicated discourse boundaries: sound, stops, and legitimate accentuation. In this way, for effective comprehension of an unfamiliar language text, consideration ought to be paid to the advancement of students' abilities in the satisfactory insight of inflection, stops, and intelligent accentuation.

3. Lexical. It is the presence of numerous new words that students highlight as a justification for the misconception of the text. We accept it is important to feature this issue in more detail. The fundamental trouble in seeing a foreign language discourse is that the language structure has long been an inconsistent help for semantic forecast, since it is the focal point of the understudy's consideration, even though the person can't transform it. Subsequently, it is important to foster the capacity to acknowledge data even within the sight of new etymological peculiarities, by sifting it, choosing it, and making a harsh thought. Students

¹ Ergasheva N.K. Application of multimedia and interactive materials in foreign language teaching in non-philological higher educational institutions // Problemy nauki., 2020. № 2 (147). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/application-of-multimedia-and-interactivematerials-inforeign-language-teaching-in-non-philological-higher-educational-institutions/> (date of access: 17.03.2020).

ought to be explicitly instructed to comprehend discourse that contains new jargon by tuning in. Unaccepted or misjudged pieces of a discourse message (word, state, express) are reestablished by students through the activity of probabilistic forecast (the capacity to foresee new things because of the known), consequently, it is important to accomplish foreseeing the significance of the explanation when the structure and content structure total solidarity. The hardships of the subsequent gathering are sociolinguistic and sociocultural. Sociolinguistic ability implies information on standards of language utilization in various circumstances what's more information on situational variations of articulation of a similar open aim; as needs are, an audience should know these variations and comprehend the purposes behind utilizing one of them with regards to a specific correspondence circumstance. Sociocultural ability suggests information on the guidelines and accepted practices of conduct of local speakers, customs, history, culture, and social arrangement of the nation of the language being examined. Subsequently, the student should have the option to see and comprehend oral text according to an intercultural point of view, which requires foundation information. Just with this information, a student can accurately decipher the discourse and non-discourse conduct of a local speaker.

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